

PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN ONLINE DISTANT LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The usage of digital technologies is arising day by day for humans learning from the past decades and it's becoming the integral part of education in future. Its importance and features are also growing for the betterment of human mankind. The Covid-19 pandemics effected all fields of the society and particularly education sector while following of social distancing. In order to keep education running, educational institutions have had to quickly adapt to the situation. This has resulted in an unprecedented push to online learning by implementing different pedagogical approaches. Many, including commercial digital learning platform providers, have rushed to provide their solutions. This study produces the connectivity and integration ratio along with pedagogical approaches in digital technologies throughout the present COVID-19 pandemic for getting optimal outcome. It addresses the following four topics: (1) the particular digital technologies that are used, (2) the specific generation who are using these digital technologies, (3) the particular activities of digital technologies that are used by people of the world., and (4) the particular effects of victimization of these digital technologies on humans throughout the pandemic. This study investigates the potential usage of digital applications like Facebook social network site to support faculty in implementing a social constructivist approach to facilitate student-centered learning. The basic purpose of this study is to review and analyze the impact of pedagogical approaches in an online distant learning through usage ratio.

Keywords: pedagogical approaches, online distant learning. Digital technologies